

Heritage-In-Making: Engagement with Young People's Cultural Practices in India

Madhavi Reddy, Savitribai Phule Pune University, India

Priya Gohad, Savitribai Phule Pune University, India

Neha Ghatpande, Gokhale Institute of Politics and Economics, Pune

Abstract

This study investigates the perceptions and practices of 'Indian Culture' among young people in India, revealing a paradoxical uniformity in their understanding of cultural inheritance. Through two case studies - a group of drumming (Dhol-Tasha Pathak) and a group of wall painters - this research explores the localised and youth-driven cultural practices in Pune city in Maharashtra, India. Employing voluntary and prominent groups among young people aged 14-25, this study examines the diverse socio-economic contexts and cultural engagement. Data collection via interviews and participant observation reveals the complex and elusive nature of culture as defined by young people, highlighting the challenges of grasping this concept in India's pluralistic society. The findings of this research indicate that digital interactions on social media platforms surpass face-to-face interactions in shaping young people's understanding of diverse cultures. Furthermore, family and friends play a pivotal role in introducing young people to cultural practices and facilitating their comprehension of 'other' cultures. The study also underscores the political and economic nuances that underlie cultural practices in public spaces in the Indian context, underscoring the need for nuanced analysis of intercultural dialogue and negotiation.

Keywords: youth cultural practices, Indian culture, intercultural dialogue, digital interactions, socio-economic contexts, cultural heritage.

Introduction

The broad spectrum of young people's cultural activities embedded in local contexts are driven by their perception of what is culturally significant to them. The emphasis of this research is on self-produced cultural and heritage understandings. Informal groups of young people are accessed to study their utilisation, negotiation and adaptation of public space for artistic, sporting and creative activities. In this research, we are focusing on two informal groups, '*Dhol Tasha Pathak*' (henceforth referred to as drumming group) and a group of young people engaged in wall painting activity (henceforth referred to as wall painting group). Young people between the age group of 16-25 years involved in these two informal groups have a substantial element of cultural participation through the activities that provide an environment for intercultural dialogue and friendship groups.

Central to the research undertaken is a 'bottom-up' approach to cultural heritage-in-the-making through close observation of the sites and cultural practices that hold meaning to young people. By interviewing young people and through participant observation, we want to understand how cultural literacy is acquired and enacted within informal and voluntary settings. The key objectives that we address are to investigate young people's experiences and

attitudes on their culture, 'other' cultures, and minorities in their respective local communities and countries. To examine the significant drivers of young people's attitudes towards others, their practices of intercultural communication across the critical environments of socio-cultural interaction, exploring young people's views on cultural/national identity and also to investigate young people's perception of social stereotypes and prejudices about culture.

This research focuses on the following research questions:

- How and why young people gain their cultural competences?
- How they experience the cultural heritage and negotiate shifting conditions of intercultural communication?
- How young people make sense of their identities concerning such discursive constructs as family, local community, nation, and Europe (or the 'West').

Methodology:

We identified young people from both the groups for the ethnographic study, secured access and started fieldwork in their respective sites. Before visiting the research sites, the field researchers were oriented towards observing the subtle nuances of cultural activities where young groups are involved. The field researchers understood not only the objectives of this work but also the variety and diversity of the youth groups they are engaging through participant observation and in-depth interviews. Regular meetings with field observers also helped in understanding the role of insider-outsider perspective of data collection.

Selection of Sites:

The two groups selected for this study include a group of performers using Indian drums (locally known as 'Dhol-Tasha Pathak ') and a group of young people involved in wall painting activity. Both groups are voluntary and prominent among young people, located in Pune city. At the same time, their activities and audience differ from each other. This selection allowed us to explore the different socio-economic environment and cultural engagement.

Group 1: Drumming group

The tradition of playing the Dhol-Tasha is an inherent part of the festivities during the 'Ganesh Festival', the most popular cultural, religious festival celebrated in Maharashtra (and among the Marathi speaking community) during the months of August-September. It celebrates Lord Ganesh (a Hindu deity) who is worshipped for his wisdom and invoked at the start of any auspicious event among Marathi Hindus. In Maharashtra especially, Ganesh festival is a significant cultural festival, which assumes a variety of political and economic overtones that get played out in the public sphere. Hitherto limited to private celebrations in Hindu households, Lokmanya Tilak (1856-1920), a prominent leader in the freedom struggle and who hailed from Maharashtra, initiated the public celebration of Ganesh festival as a way to create social consciousness and social capital to strengthen agitations against the British rule and these public celebrations continued even after the achieving independence. Even

today, these celebrations take the form of decorative installations of the Ganesh idol and tableaux on street corners that are organised and installed by members of local youth groups. At the time of installation of the idol on the first day of the festival and then on the last day at the time of immersion of the idols, there are large processions by each group. It is at the time of these processions that participants, particularly the youth, resort to using the traditional Indian drum and dance to its beat. Over time, many informal youth groups have emerged across many cities of Maharashtra, who specialise in using the drums deftly through a systematic practice before the festivity begins. These are known as 'Dhol-Tasha Pathaks' (literally, bands or groups of youth performing the drums).

For drumming group, a specific group was chosen from among the various Dhol-Tasha Pathaks which are popular in Pune city. They typically represent the shaping of cultural sensibilities in public space. The energetic atmosphere, love for music, tradition, worship towards Lord Ganesha and a passion for preserving the culture is experienced during the performance of the group. The group activities are also associated with particular ethnic traditions. Even though the pathaks (groups) mainly emerged as performers during the Ganesh festival, gradually they have become a centre of cultural politics as well.

Group 2: Wall painting group

It constitutes a group of street artists involved in a wall painting activity. This is not the first street art project to take place in the city. A lot of street art has been created by the cooperation of the local government body and NGOs. Most of the street art reflects social messages or is part of a social campaign. This particular group has refrained itself from producing similar art. Their focus is more on community engagement and telling their stories through street art.

This site was challenging to find as most of the options available were not fitting in the required age group of 14 to 25. Also, young people (of that specific age group) in India find it very difficult to engage consistently in a voluntary activity related to culture or heritage as it requires time and effort, which they do not have at their disposal (wall painting requires long hours for discussion with respective shop keepers to decide on the themes). In India this age group is very crucial from the formal academic education point of view. It is considered as a milestone for planning their career and it is therefore seen that young people of this age group mainly concentrate on their formal education and are not significantly involved in other activities. Some options explored were poetry clubs, reading or social clubs but this group of streets artists fit in the criteria as most of their members are below 25, their membership is voluntary, and their focus is to reinvent the heritage spaces of the city through street art created with community engagement.

For wall painting group, A group of young artists who makeover the shutters of old stores in one of the lanes located in old part of the city has been selected. The space is a bustling marketplace that mainly supplies raw materials, stationery, hardware and painting products etc. Most of the shop owners are from the Dawoodi Bohra sect of Islam, and some of the families have owned that business for over 100 years. Most of the businesses owned by *Bohris* in this lane are currently run by their sixth or seventh generation. It has been said that

this lane has been a major market area since 18th century. The narrow lane of 'Bohri Ali', consists of old shops which are mostly part of the apartment buildings, also very old and hold heritage value. In later years, various shops have also been owned by Hindu Marwaridi community. This lane holds significance of depicting the (religiously) mixed culture of the old Pune city.

A website dedicated to the lane is created by one of the shop owners of the lane. The following quote from the website reflects the culture of the lane.

'As Pune entered the 20th century ruled by the British, many of these shops were now well-established firms in their respective fields and had new owners as some of the earlier inhabitants moved out or migrated to other places. The market was now a confluence of a number of communities ranging from the Bohras, native Marathas, Jains, Marwaris, Gujarathis, other sects of the Muslim community and others who started speaking the language of business. All these shops and businesses made sure that Raviwar Peth and the adjoining Nana Peth, Budhwar Peth etc were a vibrant market that truly represented what the Cosmopolitan Pune stood for. They had earned a name by doing business the honest way' (www.bohriali.com)

The selected group of young street artists decided to take the shutters of these old shops as their site to paint because of the heritage value, the lane has and the stories of the shop owners. Their motivation was to bring forward this area on the Heritage Map of Pune city. Their process included interviewing shop owners to know their history, unique selling points and elements that they would like to include in the design. Artists from this group created a design for each shutter based on the space and history of the area, characteristics of the shops and story of the shop-owners.

The mainstream assumption of this lane is that it is crowded, unsafe and unclean. But after the shutter painting project by the selected group of artists, the lane's image changed, and it was brought back on the Heritage map of Pune. This made the group's work rather revolutionary.

One of the shop owners whose shutter was painted by the group, was quoted in the Pune Times article about the group. His quote was as follows,

"A Fresh Coat has brilliantly depicted stories of each store on their shutters, thus, bringing a personal connect to each shop. Walking through Bohri ali on Sunday now feels as though one is walking through an art exhibition. The focus is on these old businesses with an aim to preserve their culture and heritage." (Times of India, 2019)

One of the artists from the group also had similar assumptions before starting to work there. She explains her experience as:

"It was in my head you know, like, because it was primarily a 'Muslim Space', maybe, there were still some notions in my head, that it would be unsafe and that I have to be more vigilant etc. but working there broke down these notions for me." (Ananya, female, 24, Design student, India)

She further mentions about the space that it significantly lacked the presence of women, and initially people were suspicious of the activity as the presence of young people painting the shutters was a completely new phenomenon. The camaraderie between the shop owners and the artists grew slowly as the former understood the motive of the group.

Young artists paint the shutter with images that are inspired by the nature of the shops. They speak to the owner and understand their needs, then work on a suitable design and finally get to work on Sundays. Even though such a form of street art tries to give the city an identity, at the same time, it is prototypical of a creative form of resistance, situated between revolutionary "artists" and their audiences, which includes both authorities and society at large. This practice could lead to contentious issues involving the artist, authorities and audience (pedestrians). These groups represent art and expression of thoughts, portrayed for a larger audience and instigate their thoughts as well.

Data Collection

In engaging in this research about cultural practices of young people, there are multiple lenses through which we had looked at, especially the social context of the young people, the spaces of research sites and the cultural activities in which they are involved. This process involved frequent visits to the sites, observing their routine, young people's interactions with others, the way they practise the cultural activity and their negotiations during the process.

Gherardi and Turner (1999) contend that only well-researched data gives rise to analytical writing that informs and educates. They write,

'What is wanted is not a social shopping list which records what has been noticed, but an account of a series of interactions with the social world in a form which plausibly alerts us to the possibility of a new order not previously seen – a theoretical account'(pp.111)

Given the desire to collect rich data, qualitative research has several methods which uphold its tradition in the strategies that they employ. Ethnographic research serves as an umbrella term for gathering data from their natural environments using methods such as fieldwork, case studies, in-depth interviews, action research and other methods (Willis, 2007). The data collection was carried out through participant observation and in-depth interviews of young people participating in these activities. Based on those observations, thick ethnographic diaries were prepared, noting the daily activities and interactions of the group as well as the reflections of the researchers. The observation data was also documented in the form of small videos and photographs. The observations helped in framing the interview questions. The variation in age, gender, ethnicity and social class of the informants were taken into consideration during their selection.

Participant observations were carried out by attending the activities of the drumming group over a period of four months and for the wall painting group for one month. In drumming group, most of the participants were in their early twenties. Four male and six female participants interviewed. In terms of socio-economic diversity, a large number of participants belong to the middle class. Besides, the majority of the participants were Marathi (regional language) speaking. In wall painting group, the participants were in the age group of 20-25.

Two female and two male participants were interviewed. Most of the participants belonged to the upper-middle class and were non-Marathi and English speaking young people.

A total of 14 interviews across both the case studies, were recorded and transcribed. The interviews conducted in Marathi (regional language) were translated into English.

Data Analysis

The data was analysed initially listing a few themes using a combination of inductive and deductive methods. All of the in-depth interviews from both the case studies were coded, taking the objectives and research questions into consideration. Common themes emerging from ‘thick descriptions’ of diaries were also considered and finalised along with the interview themes after a brief discussion among lead researchers and field observers. Our research framework includes various interventions by the post-independence Indian state that not only addressed diversity in Indian culture but may also provide lessons for Europe, especially in its present conundrums regarding diversity.

We referred to formulations like Arjun Appadurai's (1990) who refer to interconnections between globalisation and culture not only in India but all over the world. We used Bucholtz's (2002) work on the anthropology of youth to document not just highly visible youth cultures but the entirety of youth cultural practice, and its interest in how identities emerge in new cultural formations that creatively combine elements of global capitalism, transnationalism, and local culture. While analysing the stereotypes and prejudices faced by young people, we sought to support the Cunningham, 2011; Mannix & Neale, 2005 work on how gender, cultural, and ethnic diversity can improve creativity and group performance, facilitate new ways of looking at problems, and allow multiple viewpoints on decisions.

Findings:

The selected drumming group is one of the well-known groups in the city. Such groups are an inherent part of the Ganesh festival in the city. It is a group activity performed during the ten days of the Ganesh festival as a public performance, but the practice sessions, including regular meetings begin around 2-3 months before the festival. The Dhol –Tasha performance was first attempted during the Ganesh festival procession in the year 1975 in the city. One of the reputed institutions in the city originally introduced this practice for preserving the traditions and inculcating the traditional beliefs in the younger generation. This attempt was followed by other organisations, and today there are approximately more than 200 such groups that have emerged and become popular, especially among the young people. The selected group was formed in the year 2004 to keep up the tradition and devotedly participates in the procession during the ten days of the Ganesh festival. The founders of this group began with 40 participants and few instruments.

At present, there are approximately 600 to 650 participants in the group we observed for the study. There is a registration process for entering the group by completing a registration form, and no fees are charged. It is a voluntary activity, and most of the participants are young people in the age group of 18 to 25 years. Though the group is engaged in a non-economic

activity, it needs financial help. The performers are always attired in a dress code of white kurta pyjamas with a specific coloured jacket and headgear. This uniform, although not very expensive, adds to the economic impact. The participants have to bear the cost of this uniform. The purchasing and maintenance of instruments require funding. The instruments usually have to be replaced after a certain period. Manufacturing these instruments is a specialised job which requires services of skilled artisans. This is also an added factor for monetary exchanges. The group receives financial support through the payments by the different Mandals (organisations). During the procession, funds are mainly utilised for the maintenance of instruments, and necessary supplies for the participants. The Young people are actively involved in performing while the financial matters are mainly driven by the elder organisers.

As the practice commences a few months in advance, space is rented out for practice sessions. The selected group conducts its practice sessions, every year, in the open area of a marriage hall in the city, but last year the area was declared as a silent zone by the police due to the growing number of groups practising in that area which caused problems to the residents living in that area. The level of noise pollution is an issue of concern. The residents have to undergo many difficulties related to noise, traffic jams and general inconvenience. This year, one of the political leaders offered them space near his bungalow, where they conducted their practice sessions. Space constraint is one of the significant issues for the group. The practice takes place, especially during the monsoons and the limited space has to be utilised among the large group. They also need space for storing their materials, especially the instruments. In that case, they have divided the group and allotted separate timings for practice.

Initially, participation in such groups was mostly male-dominated as the activity demands immense physical strength and stamina, but with the changing times, female participation in this activity has increased. The ratio of boys and girls in the group is approximately 60:40. The majority of the participants are residents of the city but commute from different parts of the city to a specific area where practice sessions are conducted. Even though it is essentially a Hindu activity, there are members in the group who are from other religions like Sikh, Christian and Muslims, although very few in numbers. There are no barriers of religion, caste, or gender for enrolling in the group. It is the peer connections which brings them to participate in these cultural activities despite their different religious backgrounds.

The second site constitutes a group of street artists involved in the wall painting activity. The group has four core members, a trained street artist, community worker, documentary filmmaker and the last one who handles their digital presence. Along with the core group members, ten young artists voluntarily engaged with the project in the capacity of creating the artwork and painting it on the streets. This group also encouraged voluntary participation of hobby artists or non-artists to come and engage with the activity on the actual day of painting. Though it is a voluntary group, they required monetary help to acquire paints and other materials to create street art. In phase 1, their material costs were taken care of by the shop owners. For phase 2, they launched a crowdfunding campaign that earned them 2894.09 EUR (as per exchange rate of May 2020)

Their first phase of work was to paint shutters of the shops based in a lane in the old part of the city. Some of the shops in this area are almost 50 or 60 years old. Most of them belong to a minority business community known as Dawoodi Bohra Muslims, and some shops are owned by the Marwadi or Jain community three whom are also minorities. This group has painted 20 shutters in the lane. The second phase of this street art project was to paint inside and visible walls in the red-light area of the city by engaging with the community of sex workers. This phase is currently halted due to difficulties in gaining access.

In this section, we present our data analysis of young people's cultural practices and experiences in Pune city of Maharashtra, India. The interviews with young people confirmed our assumption that family and close friends play a crucial role in connecting them with the vital environment of cultural practices. We were surprised by the similarities exhibited by young people to understand the concepts of culture in answering the questions. In general, young people who are above the age group of above 20 years and are working gave more complex answers compared to younger ones.

Emerging Themes and Analysis

The young people expressed a wide range of views on culture in general, reflecting their personal understanding. They often expressed the view that the current generation should follow their parents and grandparents to keep the 'culture' going. All of them have favourable views of traditional Indian culture. Many young people showed great interest in learning other/foreign languages such as German, French and Russian. They liked learning these languages because they thought that they would enjoy visiting those countries in future, one of them mentioned that they could experience the culture in a better way by knowing their language. We have hand-coded the transcribed data of Interviews with broad categories that we could observe during the initial reading of the completed transcripts. These categories took the form of more elaborate theoretical memos, and we compiled a list of questions that emerged from the data on a separate sheet of paper. We primarily relied upon manual coding to keep track of the codes that were emerging from the process.

The first theme 'Defining Culture' revolved around the different ways the young people choose to define culture and their reasons for making meaning of it in a certain way. The second theme 'Inter-Cultural Interactions' discloses the primary driving force behind young people's attitudes towards others, and their practices of intercultural communication across the critical environments around them. The third theme 'Heritage in the making' analyses how they experience the cultural heritage and negotiate the shifting conditions of intercultural communication. We also analysed the young people's views regarding national (ethnic) identity, national heritage while ascertaining how they gain cultural competence. The fourth theme 'Agents of Conflict' explores how young people perceive the social stereotypes and prejudices and also the kind of conflicts they encounter in general.

Defining Culture

To analyse the different ways in which young people make sense of culture, we start with a question of what allows the young people today to define a particular case as an instance of what a culture can be. Most of the young people defined culture almost in a similar way in their interviews as an instance of what culture means to them. We chose a few quotations from their interviews not because it is representative of how culture is defined by them but because it is also demonstrative of the elusive nature of culture. It allows for a closer examination of what exactly can be called 'culture' by a young group of people.

Culture means something by which the people are connected to our soil, our relations, the people around us... The traditions that our ancestors began or the customs that we have been following from the beginning represents our culture, for instance, dance forms represent culture or classical music, or an Indian instrument like santoor or tanpura.(Tanpura is played alongside singing). Sitar, or tabla- music represents our culture.. Books are representative of the culture, like Rugveda ...the historical sites like Taj Mahal, Qutub Minar, Char Minar, Shaniwarwada- they all represent our culture. Above all, the festivals we celebrate in India represent our unique culture and diversity. (Diya, female, 19, student, India)

For most of the young people whose interviews inform this report, responses to define what they felt about culture with how practising or foregrounding certain qualities, actions, or just feeling a certain way was what carried the essence of being a part of culture. Reflections on what culture meant to them in most cases began with actions and rituals that are age-old and still practised. Culture was repeatedly defined as 'dress code,' 'language' 'festivals', 'rituals', 'practices', 'heritage sites', 'dance, music and books'.

For some young people, culture was not a distinct concept that had to be practiced only during festivals. The culture was an overarching concept that seemed to play out in the social and the political- space.

Culture means mingling with everyone and co-existing happily with one another. It applies to how you live in your home and the city, how you treat visitors. (Lakshmi, female, 24, architect, India)

Culture is a thought process, is the thought process of a majority of people that live in a place and it is, it is umm... unspoken rules and unsaid laws.(Ajay, male, 24, management student, India)

If we consider culture is a way of life for people; for many Indians, the family is the most important social unit. There is a strong preference for extended families, consisting of two or more married couples (often of more than a single generation). Living together without many differences is a quality to be imbibed or expected among the younger generation. It is prevalent in India where people with various social, occupational, and religious backgrounds live together in close communities and participate in each other's cultural activities.

Inter-cultural interactions

India constitutes a wide variety of diverse social groups, follows its own local or regional habits, customs and cultures, and yet stands united bound by one culture, usually referred to by the phrase 'unity amidst diversity'. Today we are witnessing an increase in terms of mobility of people within the country and outside the country, either for education or for work. Young people primarily experience other cultures in shifting their local loyalty to develop national/global loyalty. Such a constellation of cultures, one nourishing the other makes way, all the while, for the emergence of a national/global culture.

Accessing information from multiple sources is vital to cultivate cultural competence in young people. Today, young people obtain much information online. In their interviews, young people stressed that they are aware of fake/unreliable sources of information on the Internet. Most of the interviewed young people from both the case studies said that they come to know other cultures through online platforms. Some young people felt that generally, books offer more reliable information compared to online information. However, they spend more time watching videos on current affairs and also sharing their own activity images in the dedicated websites (meant for drumming group) as well as social media platforms. They like to see themselves, dressed up for the activity, on social media. They enjoy the attention from their peers and followers on these different social media platforms. They sometimes use social media to connect to other cultural activities in the city.

During the practice sessions at drumming group, we observed that the activity is a part of celebrating the Hindu festivities of Ganesh Festival. All the young boys and girls are from the same religious community. The idea of a youth culture that the young can regard as their own, with specific elements and values, including the ability to accept diversity and tolerance towards others' beliefs appears sharp in the interviews of young people. The interviewed students live in an environment of cultural diversity, especially in the urban and semi-urban areas. They also mentioned that diversity of values within the local community, gender, class and caste differences does not matter to them when they are together practising the activity. They also appreciated that the organisers have never asked about their caste details while enrolling for the practice sessions. The opinions, the interests and the ways of behaving are all aspects that those interviewed consider as relevant in defining diversity among equals.

Interestingly for Indian youngsters, family members especially parents, grandparents, close friends, and their school to some extent, are the major driving forces behind their attitudes towards others and their practices of socio-cultural interactions. When we asked about what motivated them to join the drumming group one of them said:

I started playing (dhol-tasha)when I was very young. I am playing since I was four or five years old, means my grandfather used to play my maternal uncle used to play, and my father used to play tasha very well and he plays it even now for our group or for any other function.(Shirish, Male, 24, runs the family business, India)

One young girl believed that she got to know different cultures and customs through friends or classmates of different origins to her own, thereby, she learned about other cultures, as well as opening her horizons when it comes to cultural diversity. When she went on a semester exchange programme with a French Design School, she explains her experience as:

Twenty of us are from different countries, and I became very close to a few of them. So, even now I maintain those relations with my 'South African Sister' and then I have many close friends in 'Mexico' and 'Spain', and we visited each other's home. They also came to India during my sister's wedding and things like that. So, I feel like now, I have a mixed bag of friends... kind of extended family members. (Ananya, female, 24, Design student, India)

The majority of the young people reported that they have not volunteered to join cultural activities on their initiative. It was always a member of the family or a friend who introduced them to activities. For the parents, activities like joining the drumming group (Dhol-Tasha) have legitimacy and help their children to socialise and stay connected with culture. This leads to encouragement by parents for joining these groups. One of them has volunteered as part of the school programme since many of the city schools have such programmes.

Heritage- in- the making

This theme questions how young people experience cultural heritage and negotiate the shifting conditions of inter-cultural communication. Interestingly, when we began to talk directly about "cultural heritage" with them, we noticed that they do not consider many of their own activities like playing dhol-tasha and interests as a part of culture. They are unable to grasp that they can be part of the heritage-in-making. The young people expressed their familiarity with the heritage sites in the city as cultural heritage but were unable to acknowledge the intangible Cultural Heritage through human agency.

Young people define themselves in various ways and often are characterised by their fluid identities. Some of them defined themselves as Maharashtrians, others as South-Indians, others claim both identities, yet others refer to their (or their parents) states of origin; finally, all of them see themselves as "citizens of India". Young people interviewed point out that they learn within their own family about the diversity of customs and traditions, as they compare family members who pertain to different generations and geographical origins.

In India, we consider territorially defined regions as the most inclusive, which has historical, linguistic and socio-cultural connotations. Apart from the historical importance of the region, it has now taken many ethnic characteristics within its ambit. Given the complexity of identity in diverse India, where ethnicity alone can only inadequately define regional communities such as the Oriyas, Bengalis, Tamils and Maharashtrians (People from respective states of Orissa, West –Bengal, Tamilnadu and Maharashtra)a regional perspective provides a more useful analytical approach.

In explaining the national/ cultural identity, the young people of migrant backgrounds position themselves by their state identities, depending on their family origin. Both birthplace and language spoken at home have a bearing on their cultural identification, whether between state and nation, or both at the same time. In our interviews, we noticed that the concept of

cultural heritage, like the concept of culture is very abstract and not understood by young people.

Surprisingly, many of the young people identified themselves with respect to their everyday practices at home and with the friends who, according to them, can uphold the cultural heritage. They mention about values that they learn at home, for example, praying to god, respecting elders, pride being a member of a particular religion, helping the poor, dressing style and culinary habits, i.e. the values that are generally learned in the family can pass on the cultural heritage of the country, and there is a need to preserve those values.

When we investigated how these young people gain their cultural competence, many girls came up with behaviours of active listening, demonstrating empathy towards others that will help them to create a conducive and welcoming environment and establish an appreciation of the similarities and differences among cultures which is common in many parts of India. *"It is like small things for me it would be; I am a Muslim we still do, we still put Rangoli and we still put diyas for Diwali like we do for my culture, you know umm..."*(Shahida, female, 25, pursuing her masters in Melbourne).

Agents of Conflict

The stereotypes of a particular social group that are held by a society have an impact on how all members of that group are viewed and treated by the society. Stereotyping involves the imputation of unchanging and inflexible characteristics to all members of a particular group.

In addressing the perception of social stereotypes and prejudices by young people, we enquired about the sites/ agencies in which they are embedded, and young people found reservations in education, caste and gender were the prominent recurring conflicts that were invoked. "Reservation for certain caste has been misused till now in India. It has been only used for politics....everybody ignores the poor. I hesitate to speak because I don't want to lose my friends on this...." (Deepak, male, 21, management student, India).

Though the literature about discrimination of caste and class predominantly informs that an upper class /caste inherits the 'cultural capital' therefore enjoys a special status and acceptance in the society. Akash, a 18-year-old college student, says being from an upper class/caste background also brings a barrier in specific contexts to mingle with his friends of diverse backgrounds.

I feel like uprooting the caste system altogether. Majorly, I do not believe in the caste system. Despite being a Brahmin, I do not wear anything around my wrist or neck. All I have are these that Sanket-dada tied on my wrists as a symbol of dhvaj (flag) and I do not remove them ever. These have been given to me by my guru. Other than that, I tie other things on my wrist as a culture. But that is only when there is a puja, as I don't like discriminating based on caste, that I am a Brahmin.(Akash, male, 18, college student)

From interviews of the young people, they were seen grappling with the intertwining of the issues of caste and class in India. One of the young participants who comes from the lower caste community says that he has never faced any discrimination by citing the reason that his

family now belongs to the upper class and he socialises with a class of people that is in denial of the existence of caste.

I hang out with media college people where everyone's supposed to be woke. You know and everyone is supposed to know everything and you know, we are supposed to be the top 1% of the most educated minds, the young minds of the country, we don't acknowledge caste. We're like it doesn't exist. When we ask (young) people, what do you think about the caste system? They say it is there but it's very inconvenient because of reservation, it's not fair. And I am like, but if you are a brahmin (upper caste) then do you think what your ancestors did to them (lower caste people), so do you think that was fair? (Aniket, male, 22, media student)

Discussion

Engaging with young people's cultural practices allowed us not only to understand them but also situate them as a staging ground for integration into the adult community, which often obscures young people's own cultural agency. By contrast, many sociological inquiries suggested youth cultures as central objects of study, whether as deviant subcultures or as class-based sites of resistance; if not both, one of the research sites of our case study displays this character.

In a technology-oriented world, youth has begun to take shape, sparked by the stimuli of both modernity and traditions in an ambivalent engagement with local contexts. This broad and interdisciplinary approach revisits the questions raised in this framework while introducing new conflicts that arise under the current economic, political, and cultural conditions in India. The anthropology of youth is characterized by its attention to the agency of young people, its concern to document not just highly visible youth cultures but the entirety of youth cultural practice, and its interest in how identities emerge in new cultural formations that creatively combine elements of global capitalism, transnationalism, and local culture. (Bucholtz, 2002)

This notion of inclusiveness and exclusiveness reconfigured the young people's notion of tradition versus modernity, high values versus no values, the contestations which surface in everyday life. The cultural practices youth engages today determine their nature in terms of finding the balance between the binaries of tradition and modernity. The participant observation of research sites and interviews of young people confirms it. The data reveals that the majority of young people from a middle-class background and belonging to the Hindu religion take pride in joining the cultural activity of dhol-tasha pathak. It is observed that some parents accompany them to the practice sessions. Though the young people show no interest in active politics, they are very much aware of a political overtone of their activity in the public sphere. (Hindu nationalism as an ideology matching with the majority politics in India). In contrast, the majority of young people in the wall painting activity group who came from an affluent background believe in the plurality of cultures which is represented in their group composition as well as their cultural practice. Our interviews with young people reinforce that face-to-face interactions are the foundation in building relationships with people from different cultural backgrounds, at the same time not denying the fact that they do engage in digital platforms to learn about different cultures and cultural practices which are of interest to them.

Conclusion:

Bringing together, the discourse of cultural practices in India, the two case studies illustrate a view on the lived experiences surrounding the formation of cultural competence among young people. Additionally, the interviews offer more significant insights on how young people make sense of culture, by bringing to the fore the multiple dimensions of the process in which they make sense of cultural heritage and belonging.

One of the critical findings that run through the different levels of understanding young people and their engagement with cultural practices relates to the limited presence of Europe or west, dimension while participating in their cultural activities. The focus on national belonging and significant underplaying of post-national frames of reference are confirmed through young people's interviews. The dominant approach to culture, emerging through the responses from the young consisted of a liberal alongside a traditional (Hindu) strand, underlying national parameters of belonging. At the same time, we identified normative and values-based notions of culture, and an enhanced focus on linking culture, religion, and region with their identities.

Participant observation of research sites and young people's responses evoked new dimensions of intercultural interactions and cultural identity focusing on a single dimension of it; thus gender stereotyping, caste and religion overshadowed other intersecting aspects of identification paving the way to an essentialist understanding of their engagement with the culture. The cultural practices of the young in India reflect the majoritarian politics making everyday life more alike to practices of the Hindu community, which is evidenced through one of the research sites. Although many cultural practices in India attempt to be more inclusive eventually, the dominant discourse of Hindu practices sufficed.

Policy Recommendations:

Our data points out certain policy recommendations for enhancing cultural participation of young people.

- Create and reinforce synergy between youth and stakeholders of cultural heritage – promotion and preservation of cultural activities requires the collaboration of various stakeholders, ranging from site managers to the local community, and from heritage experts to young volunteers.
- Expand the outreach of the projects with proper funding which promotes a regional and international exchange of cultures- As some of the cultural activities are recognized for their 'outstanding universal value', (for example the wall painting activity), it is vital to raise awareness among young people to the existence/coexistence of different cultures across the world.

- Creating inclusive public spaces for young people – there is a need to introduce innovations in existing traditional cultural practices as well as when young people are trying to create new cultural spaces, it is necessary to ensure safe public spaces and support from the government and civil society.
- Promoting the digital presence of themes related to culture and heritage as an authentic source of information -websites of museums, heritage sites need to be developed and they should be youth-friendly.

Acknowledgements

This work is part of the larger Project titled CHIEF (Cultural Heritage and Identities of Europe's Future) Grant Agreement no: 770464 funded by the European Union. We thank the organisers of the selected informal groups for their kind permission to conduct fieldwork. We are also thankful to Madhura Joshi and Shubhangi Satkar who assisted us in conducting the field work.

References

Appadurai, A. (1990). 'Disjuncture and Difference in the Global Cultural Economy', *Theory Culture & Society*, 7, London, Newbury Park and New Delhi: Sage Publications, pp. 295-310

Bucholtz, M. (2002). 'Youth and Cultural Practice.' *Annual Review of Anthropology*, 31(1):525-552 [DOI: 10.1146/annurev.anthro.31.040402.085443]

Cunningham, G. B. (2011). 'The LGBT advantage: Examining the relationship among sexual orientation diversity, diversity strategy, and performance'. *Sport Management Review*, 14(4), pp. 453-461.

Gherardi, S., & Turner, B. (1999). 'Real men don't collect soft data'. In: Bryman, A., & Burgess, R. (Eds.), *Qualitative Research*. London: Sage Publications, pp. 103-118

Hall, S. (1999). 'Whose Heritage? Un-settling' The Heritage', *Reimagining the Post-nation*. *Third Text*, 13 (49), pp. 3-13

Lukose, R. (2009). *Liberalisation's Children: Gender, Youth, and Consumer Citizenship in Globalizing India*. NC: Duke University Press.

Mannix, E., & Neale, M. A. (2005). 'What differences make a difference? The promise and reality of diverse teams in organizations'. *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 6(2), pp. 31–55.

Nandy A. (1989). 'The Political Culture of the Indian State'. *Another India*, 118 (4), The MIT Press on behalf of American Academy of Arts & Sciences, pp. 1-26

Parekh, R. (2019). 'One shutter at a time, group of artists sets out to give BohriAali a facelift', *The Times of India (Pune)*, 7 May. Available at: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/pune/one-shutter-at-a-time-group-of-artists-sets-out-to-give-bohri-aali-a-facelift/articleshow/69208491.cms>

Willis, J.W. (2007). 'Foundations of qualitative research'. *Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications*.